

Wilkie Syndrome Complicating Peptic Ulcer-Related Stenosis: A Unique Clinical Case

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Abstract

Peptic ulcers are a leading cause of gastric outlet obstruction, with endoscopic treatment combined with medical therapy for *Helicobacter pylori* infection being the gold standard. Weight loss is one of the major complications of gastric outlet obstruction. Authors presented the case of a patient who experienced chronic gastric pain, vomiting and weight loss. The initial oesophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) revealed peptic ulcer stenosis and the presence of *H. pylori*. Although medical treatment was initiated, there was no significant improvement. Further investigation using an abdominal CT scan revealed the development of superior mesenteric artery syndrome, which required surgical intervention. This case highlights the potential complications of *H. pylori* infection, particularly weight loss, and emphasizes the possibility of progression to superior mesenteric artery syndrome.

Introduction

Superior mesenteric artery syndrome (also known as Wilkie syndrome) [9] and peptic ulcer are two main cause of gastric and duodenal stenosis for adults. We report a rare case of a patient presenting chronic vomiting that occurs to have Wilkie's syndrome associated with a stenotic peptic ulcer

Case Report

A 44 years old patient smoker of tobacco and cannabis, who reported a chronic epigastric pain with alimentary postprandial vomiting evolving since 14 years associated to an unquantified weigh loss. The clinical examination showed a normal BMI at 20 kg/m², abdominal examination reveals an epigastric tenderness with a succussion splash without sign of dehydration or malnutrition.

An oesophagogastroduodenoscopy revealed a large gastric ulcer in the angle and inflammatory pyloric stenosis. Biopsies were taken and the histopathological results revealed no evidence of malignancy, though they did detect the presence of *Helicobacter pylori*.

A thoraco-abdominal CT scan showed wall thickening of the greater curvature, which was irregular in appearance and enhanced after PDC injection. The maximum thickness was 30 mm (Figure 1), and there was a reduction in the aorto-mesenteric angle of 12.5°.

More Information

How to cite this article: Kenza BT, Ilias EA, Anas EW, Amal H, Driss E, Rachid B, Jai R, Farid C. Wilkie Syndrome Complicating Peptic Ulcer-Related Stenosis: A Unique Clinical Case. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2025;3(3):135-7.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(3).20

Keywords:

Peptic ulcer, Stenosis, Wilkie syndrom.

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A follow-up CT scan showed the same appearance, with a reduction in the distance between the aorta and the superior mesenteric artery to 3.3 mm and a reduction in the aorto-mesenteric angle to 9° (Figure 2). This was concluded to be Wilkie syndrome with gastritis.

Figure 1: Image of the CT Scan Showing the Thickening of the Greater Curvature

Biological tests were normal, showing no signs of malnutrition or dehydration, with a hemoglobin level of 13.6 g/dL, albumin at 41 g/L, Na⁺ at 137 mEq/L, K⁺ at 4.2 mEq/L, urea at 0.29 g/L, and creatinine at 11.5 mg/L. The patient received a medical treatment for his ulcers and eradication of *Helicobacter pylori* by the combination of bismuth subcitrate/ metronidazole/

tetracycline and omeprazole, without a regression of the symptomatology.

Figure 2: Image of the CT Scan Showing the Distance between the SMA and the Aorta and Angle between Them

Given the lack of improvement in his symptoms it was decided with the patient approval that gastroenterostomy should be performed. The patient was admitted for surgery, the surgical exploration under laparotomy showed a gastric stasis with a pyloric stenosis (Figure 3), the patient had a gastrojejunostomy with ileal anastomosis.

The follow-up was normal, with alimentation authorized at D-3 post-op and the patient discharged at D-5. Follow-up consultations were made at 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months, showing a complete disappearance of the symptoms.

Figure 3: Image Showing the Pyloric Stenosis

Discussion

Gastroduodenal ulcers are a common inflammatory affection seen predominately in males between 20-40 years old. Peptic localization is frequent and it's the major cause of gastric outlet obstruction [1]. Its annual incidence varies in developed countries is 1-3 per

100,000. However, it is still relatively frequent in Africa with an annual incidence of 4-13 per 100,000 [2,3,10]. Gastric outlet obstruction (GOO) is a condition caused by the mechanical compression and obstruction of the distal stomach, pyloric antrum, or duodenum [11]. Its origins can be benign or malignant conditions with the most common causes including peptic ulcer and gastric cancer, in our case the obstruction was due to a neglected ulcer [1,11]

In our case the gastric outlet obstruction caused an important weight loss leading to the diminution of distance between aorta and superior mesenteric artery, measured at 3.4 mm, with reduction of aorto-mesenteric angle measuring 9°.

Superior mesenteric artery syndrome, also known as Wilkie's syndrome, is a rare clinical condition first described by Carl von Rokitansky during an autopsy in 1842. In 1927, Wilkie published the first series of cases involving around 75 patients [4,12]. The syndrome is defined as a compression of the third portion of the duodenum in between the SMA and the abdominal aorta [13] due to a smaller angle between these 2 vessels (<22°) and distance between them <8 mm which are normally between 25° to 60°, and 10 to 28 mm, leading to the symptoms of a high gastrointestinal obstruction [5].

Several factors have been implicated in the development of superior mesenteric artery syndrome. These include congenital causes, such as a low insertion of the superior mesenteric artery (SMA) or a high insertion of Treitz's angle; spinal trauma; and abdominal surgery, weight loss and burns.

SMA syndrome may present a chronic or acute symptomatology. An acute presentation is typically characterized by signs and symptoms of severe

gastrointestinal obstruction [14]. Patients with chronic conditions such as our own may present with long-standing, vague abdominal symptoms or recurrent episodes of abdominal pain associated with vomiting [14]. Less common symptoms include oesophageal reflux, early satiety and a sensation of fullness due to increased gastroduodenal transit time, and gastric distension [14].

Conclusion

In our case the double localization of the obstruction forced to adapt the surgery for both pathology. Benign Gastric outlet obstruction is treated endoscopically or surgically with various including pyloroplasty, sub-total gastrectomy and gastro-jejunosomy [6]. SMA's treatment is based on many surgical treatment including vascular procedure: derotation procedure, transposition of the SMA to the infrarenal aorta and visceral procedures: duodenal circular drainage, anterior transposition of the third part of duodenum, Billroth II gastrectomy, gastrojejunostomy, Strong's procedure and duodenojejunostomy[7,15]. We choose the gastrojejunostomy because the patient had two obstacles with the upper is pyloric, and less morbidity has been reported with it compared to other procedures [8].

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